

The number of Learned Societies in Europe

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Federation of Finnish Learned Societies

In historical perspective, learned societies constitute, along with universities and other kinds of research performing organisations, the foundation of contemporary European academia (Ellis, 2020). Yet, surprisingly little information and research exists on their current number, forms of organisations and operation, or contributions to scientific and societal impact of research in Europe. In this work in progress paper we present a rough preliminary estimate of the number of learned societies in Europe to be around 9.000.

Background

Since the 15th century, learned societies - voluntary non-profit organisations involving academics - have existed for the advancement of scholarship, research, disciplines, publishing and public understanding of science. In English-language literature, a learned society (Hopkins, 2011) can also be referred to as a learned association (Bennett, 2013), scholarly association (Willinsky, 2005), scholarly societies (Stapleton (2019), or scientific association (Delicado et al., 2014). Occasionally, the term professional society is also used (TBI Communications, 2014). Indeed, some research on learned societies takes into account both learned societies and professional associations (Delicado et al., 2014; TBI Communications, 2014).

The most well-known learned societies are the national science academies, in which membership is typically based on invitation and merit. However, there also exists a much broader archipelago of local, national and international societies, whose membership is open to all academics, and often also to interested professionals and citizens. Publishing scientific journals and books has traditionally been an important part of the activities of learned societies (Late et al., 2020; Ware & Mabe, 2012) but they take also other various activities including arranging conferences, supporting research, and popularising knowledge (e.g. Delicado et al., 2014; Korkeamäki et al. 2019).

Number of societies in selected countries

Although there is no formal information available about the number of learned societies in Europe, there are lists of societies in some countries and lists of societies in specific fields. In order to estimate the number of societies across Europe we retrieved lists of societies from 11 countries presented in Table 1. The information was retrieved from web pages from different institutions (such as Federations of Learned Societies), Wikipedia, country specific databases and scholarly publications. Used data sources are listed at the end of this publication. However, it is difficult to estimate what is included in the lists (for example found from Wikipedia) and what

is not since we have not been in a position to check the accuracy of lists at our disposal. Although we only used sources claiming to list learned/scientific/scholarly societies/associations it is possible that “learned society” may have been defined somewhat differently in some of the lists. With these limitations in mind, some estimates can be calculated based on available information.

Table 1. Number of learned societies and population in selected countries

Country	Number of societies	Population
Austria	222	8 950 544
Finland	295	5 541 806
France	298	67 445 000
Germany	374	83 121 363
Ireland	54	4 977 400
Italy	169	59 126 079
Poland	300	38 169 000
Portugal	376	10 298 252
Spain	84	47 394 223
Switzerland	92	8 680 890
UK	199	67 081 234
Total	2463	400 785 791

In total, we identified 2463 societies in 11 countries. The number of societies ranges from 50 to 400 among the larger and smaller countries (based on population), and this makes sense as there can reasonably be only x many field specific societies per country. In some fields, such as history, it may be common that there are local or regional societies in addition to the national ones. It is likely that in bigger countries the number of members/society is probably larger. It is beyond this working paper to analyse and establish the possible reasons for the differences in the number of societies between countries (e.g. Germany and Spain). The average number of societies based on this information per country was 224. However, this is only a rough estimate, due to the insecurities in our data. True number of societies is probably even larger since it is likely that there are societies that were left out from our data.

Estimation of the number of societies in ERA countries

The information presented above was used to estimate the number of societies in 27 Eu countries and 19 associated countries (see European Commission). This totals 46 ERA countries.

Table 2. Three scenarios to estimate the number of societies in 46 ERA countries

	Number of ERA countries	Number of societies/country	Total number of societies
Scenario 1	46	224	10 304
Scenario 2	46	50-400	2 300-18 400
Scenario 3	40	224	8 960

There are different options to estimate the number of these societies (see Table 2). In the first scenario it is assumed that the average number of societies in all 46 ERA countries is 224 based on our analysis of 11 countries. Second scenario uses the lower and upper numbers from 11 countries to provide a range for the number of societies in the 46 ERA countries. In the third scenario we left out the six very smallest countries (less than 1 million habitants; Cyprus, Faroe Islands, Iceland, Luxembourg, Malta and Montenegro), resulting in (224 societies x 40 countries) 8.960 societies in total. It is likely that small countries have learned societies as well, however, to a smaller extent. In light of the uncertainties related to the data we tentatively prefer scenario 3 to give the most useful preliminary estimate. To be able to make more accurate estimations, societies in all countries should be mapped by experts that have knowledge about the traditions and structures of scientific organizations in specific countries.

Conclusion

Although being established and well known organizations, there is only fragmented information available of European learned societies. Our data shows however, that the number of societies across Europe is remarkable. We identified 2.463 societies in 11 European countries and estimate the total number of societies in the ERA area to be at least 9.000 societies. However, data sources used are not formal and the provided numbers and calculations should be taken with caution.

References:

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Data sources:

Austria: The Federation of Austrian Scientific Societies: <https://vwgoe.at/>

Finland: Federation of Finnish Learned Societies: <https://tsv.fi/fi/toiminta/jasenseurat> (in Finnish)

France: Wikipedia:

https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Liste_de_soci%C3%A9t%C3%A9s_savantes_scientifiques_en_France#Sciences_humaines_et_sociales

German: Schimank, Uwe. (1988). Scientific associations in the German research system—Results of an empirical study. *Knowledge in Society* 1(2): 69—85.

See also Wikipedia: https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wissenschaftliche_Gesellschaft

Ireland: Wikipedia: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Irish_learned_societies

Italy: Italian non-profit organizations:

<https://italianonprofit.it/enti/parole-chiave-ricerca-scientifica/>

See also: <https://www.cnr.it/en/accordi-partnership/fondazioni-associazioni>

Poland: http://www.tnp.org.pl/Towarzystwa+naukowe+w+Polsce_tom_1.pdf

Portugal: Scientific Societies in Contemporary Science database:

<http://www.socsci.ics.ul.pt/baseassoc>

Spain: Federation of Scientific Societies of Spain: <https://cosce.org/sociedades/>

Switzerland: Swiss Academy of Sciences:

https://scnat.ch/en/scnat/for_the_network/annual_report

UK: Wikipedia:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Category:Learned_societies_of_the_United_Kingdom